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ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF FUNGI SPECIES RESPONSIBLE FOR FRUIT ROT OF OKRA IN WUKARI TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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Kyugah Jacob Tersur

Department of Biological Sciences, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State

Madinatu, Yusuf

Department of Plant Sciences, Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State

Audu Sanusi Kiri

Department of Plant Sciences, Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State

Zubairu Gaddafi Jimeta

Department of Plant Sciences, Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State

Abstract

This work was designed to isolate and identify fungi associated with fruit rot of okra in Wukari local Government area of Taraba State. Samples of diseased okra fruits were collected from five markets randomly in the study location. The infected fruits were collected using a sterile paper bag and conveyed to the Microbiology laboratory of Federal University Wukari, under aseptic condition for the isolation of the causal organisms. Small pieces of lesions were surfaced sterilized with alcohol and inoculated on prepare plates of potato dextrose agar (PDA). After 48 to 62 hours of inoculation, when fungal growth from lesions was visible, fungi were sub cultured on to a fresh PDA media to obtain pure cultures. Pure isolated fungi were identified according to recommended references and fungi atlas. Four fungal species responsible for fruit rot of okra were isolated. The isolated fungi were *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus stolonifera*, *Rhizopus oryzae* and *Fusarium oxysporum*. Pathogenicity test was carried out to confirm if these pathogens were responsible for the fruit rot of the okra, similar symptoms observed in the original sample brought from the market were still observed in the healthy okra inoculated with the pathogens isolated in the laboratory conforming with Koch's postulate. Rots caused by the pathogens cause economic loss by reducing the quality of the okra and it shelf life therefore causing financial loss to farmers. If not check properly and consume, the infected okra can cause health challenge to the consumers.

Keywords: Isolation, Identification, Fruit rot, Okra and Species
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Introduction

Okra was earlier included in genus *Hibiscus*, section *Abelmoschus* in the family *Malvaceae* (Mishra *et al.*, 2021). The section *Abelmoschus* was subsequently proposed to be raised to the rank of distinct genus (Méndez-López *et al.*, 2023). The wider use of *Abelmoschus* was subsequently accepted in the taxonomic and contemporary literature. This genus is distinguished from the genus *Hibiscus* by the characteristics of the calyx, spatulate, with five short teeth, connate to the corolla and caduceus after flowering (Mishra *et al.*, 2021). Taking classification of Van Borssum Waalkes as the starting point, an up-to-date classification was adopted at the International Okra Workshop held at National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (NBPGR) in 1990 (IBPGR 1991). According to Kumar *et al.* (2020), there are several species of *Abelmoschus*, and *A. esculentus* is the most important of all these species. In Nigeria, there are two distinct seasons for okra, the peak and the lean seasons (Bamire and Oke, 2003). During the lean season (November to June) okra fruit are produced in low quantities, scarce and expensive to get (Bamire and Oke, 2003). In the peak season (July to October), it is produced in large quantities much more than what the local populace can consume

Kaur *et al.* (2021) reported that proper processing, preservation, marketing and utilization of okra is necessary to arrest the wastage being experienced during the peak season due to problem of storage facilities and diseases of Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus L.*), commonly known as lady's finger is a warm-season vegetable crop belonging to the Malvaceae family, widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions (Gemede *et al.*, 2022). Native to Africa, okra is a versatile crop grown for its tender pods, which are consumed fresh, cooked, or processed. Recent studies confirm that West Africa remains a primary center of genetic diversity for okra, hosting a vast number of its accessions (Mishra *et al.*, 2021). The crop is therefore far more heavily represented in West Africa than in any other part of the world. It is an annual crop with a life-span ranging from 1 to 5 months depending on the species. The seeds are round, greyish and relatively large (about 1.5 to 3 mm). Its adaptability to diverse agroecological conditions, including high temperatures and moderate drought, makes it a staple in many farming systems (Kaur *et al.*, 2021). In Nigeria, okra is a significant horticultural crop, valued for its role in food security, income generation, and cultural diets (Ibrahim and Bello, 2022).

The economic importance of okra in Nigeria cannot be overstated. It is a major source of livelihood for smallholder farmers, contributing to rural economies through local and regional markets (Ojo *et al.*, 2022). Okra's high demand in urban centers and export potential to neighboring countries further enhance its economic value. The crop's short growth cycle allows for multiple harvests annually, providing a steady income stream (Oyalede *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, okra cultivation supports agro-based industries, including seed production and processing, creating employment opportunities. Nutritionally, okra is a powerhouse, rich in vitamins (A, C, and K), minerals (calcium and potassium), and dietary fiber (Kaur *et al.*, 2021). Its mucilaginous pods are valued for their role in improving digestion and managing blood sugar levels. In Nigeria, okra is a key ingredient in soups and stews, such as "egusi" and "ogbono," making it integral to culinary traditions (Akanbi *et al.*, 2010). The leaves are also consumed as a leafy vegetable, enhancing its nutritional contribution to diets. In Nigeria's Southern and Northern Guinea Savannah agroecological zones, okra cultivation thrives due to favorable climatic conditions, including adequate rainfall and well-drained soils (Ojo *et al.*, 2022). Changes in weather significantly influence the growth pattern and productivity of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus L.*) (Oyelade *et al.*, 2021). Okra is sensitive to low temperatures and develops poorly below 15°C (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). Recent studies indicate that okra requires high temperatures, ideally around 30–35°C, and long day lengths for optimal growth and development (Singh and Singh, 2022). Research on weather requirements for high-yield okra in tropical regions suggests that minimum and maximum temperatures of 18°C and 35°C, respectively, are ideal for robust growth (Adebayo, 2021). Optimal temperatures between 25 and 40°C have been observed to enhance okra growth and yield (Musa *et al.*, 2022), while a critical day length of approximately 12.5 hours is necessary for flower initiation and fruit yield (Ojo and Oladiran, 2020). Evenly distributed rainfall of about 750 mm and relative humidity between 90–95% have been shown to improve okra performance (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2022). However, lower temperatures ranging from 28.9 to 29.2°C (maximum) and 17.9 to 19.8°C (minimum), combined with shorter day lengths of 5.2 to 5.7 hours, can increase flower production (Sharma *et al.*, 2021). This study is aimed at isolating and identifying pathogens responsible for fruit rot of okra in Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

The study was conducted in Wukari town, Wukari local government area of Taraba State. Wukari is the headquarters of Wukari local Government Area in Taraba State, Nigeria. The town lies within the coordinates 7° 15'N 9° 47'E and 7.8° N9.7° E. It has an area of 4.308km and population of 214.546 according to 2006 National population census of Nigeria. Taraba state is situated in the north eastern part of Nigeria and lies within the Northern guinea savannah belt. It has an annual rainfall of about 150 mm-200 mm with a mean temperature of 25°C and a maximum temperature of 39°C Taraba state diary (2010).

Sample Collection

A total of five hundred okra fruits (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) were obtained from five different markets. These include: Wukari new market, Wukari old market, Wukari yam market, Federal University Wukari market and Allah-yisa market all in Wukari town between the months of July, 2016 and October 2016. Purposive and simple random sampling technique were employed. Ten traders were selected using simple random technique. Ten okra fruits were randomly selected from each trader, making it a total of 100 fruits from each market. Thirty healthy okra fruits were later obtained in the same markets for the pathogenicity test. All the samples collected were placed in sterile polythene bags separately labeled and transported to the Biological Sciences Laboratory, Federal University Wukari, for isolation and identification.

Sterilization of Glass Wares

All the glass wares first washed with tap water and detergent solution. They were then rinsed with distilled water and air dried. The glass petri-dishes were wrapped with aluminium foil and autoclave at 160⁰ C for one hour (1 hr). They were allowed to drop for 30 minutes before usage to avoid cracking.

Preparation of Media

Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) was used for fungal cultures, and it was prepared according to manufacturer's instructions, 3.9 g in 100 ml of distilled water and autoclaved at 121°C for 15mins. It was allowed to cool to 37 °C before pouring in to 90 mm petri dishes, and then kept to solidify. Streptomycin was added as a bacteriostatic agent to inhibit the growth of bacteria in the medium.

Isolation of Fungi

The fungi associated with Okra fruit rots were isolated using the blotter method as recommended by the International Seed Health Testing Association (1976). The okra fruits were cut into sections with a sterilized knife. The sectioned fruits were surface sterilized with 70% ethanol for three minutes and rinsed in three changes of sterile distilled water to remove surface contaminants. The sterilized sectioned fruits were blotch dried between filter papers and plated on already prepared PDA media. The plates were incubated at room temperature for 3 days before sub-culturing on new sets of PDA plates. The sub- cultures were incubated for 5-7 days and then sub-cultured repeatedly on new sets of PDA plates until pure culture of the isolates were obtained.

Sub-Culturing

When fungal growth from the lesions was visible, fungi were sub-cultured on to freshly prepared PDA to obtain pure cultures for identification. Fungi were continuously sub-cultured until pure isolates were obtained. The pure fungal cultures were stored safely in the refrigerator at 4°C to prevent any further fungal growth in the plate. Once fungal colonies emerged, small portions of the growing fungus were transferred onto fresh PDA plates using a sterile needle to obtain pure isolates without contaminants.

Identification of the Isolates

The fungal isolates were subjected to certain comparative morphological studies by an image and analysis system using published descriptions in a mycological atlas. This was followed by a slide mount of each isolates. The cultural and morphological characteristics were matched with those available in the mycological atlas by watanebe (2002) and other books by Bannett and Hunter (1999), Alexopoulos *et al.* (2002), Agrios (2005) and Ellis *et al.* (2007) and identification atlas by Watanebe (2002). They were then identified accordingly.

Pathogenicity Test

To ascertain pathogenicity of the various fungi that were isolated, the approach of Balogun *et al.* (2005) was adapted. Similar healthy fruits were surfaced sterilized with 70% alcohol and rinsed in sterile distilled water. With a 3 mm diameter sterile cork borer, 2 cm long cylindrical cores were removed from each fruit; discs of 7-day old cultures of each isolate were removed from agar plates and placed in the bored holes on each fruit. Vaseline jelly was smeared to completely seal each hole to prevent external infection before incubating for 10 days. The control was inoculated with disc of solidified potato dextrose agar medium. Fruits were inoculated in three replicates. Rot symptoms developed with different fungal isolates were compared to the natural original rots.

Results and Discussion

Isolated fungi

The following fungi were isolated from the okra fruit with symptoms of rot collected randomly from five different markets within Wukari metropolis.

Asperginus niger, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Rhizopus oryzae* and *Fusarium oxysporum*. The colonial morphology on PDA and photomicrographs of isolated fungi as shown in plate (1 to 4).

Plate 1a: Seven-day-old Culture of *Aspergillus niger* on PDA showing Black mycelia.

Plate 1b: Micrographs of *Aspergillus niger* (Van Tiegh) Under Light Microscope (x40) showing sporangium and spores.

Plate 2a Seven-day-old Culture of *Rhizopus stolonifer* on PDA showing cottony white mycelia.

Plate 2b: Micrographs of *Rhizopus stolonifer* Under Light Microscope (x40) showing sporangium and Sporangiospore.

Plate3a: Seven-day-old Culture of *Rhizopus oryzae* on PDA showing dark brown mycelia.

Plate 3b: Micrograph of *Rhizopus oryzae* Under Light Microscope (x40) showing interwoven sporangiospore on sporangium.

Brownish white mycelia

Plate 4a: Seven-day-old Culture of *Fusarium oxysporum* on PDA showing brownish mycelia.

Conidiophores

Conidia

Plate 4b: Micrograph of *Fusarium oxysporum* Under Light Microscope (x40) showing conidiophores and conidia.

Discussion

Four fungi were isolated from okra fruits using the blotter method as recommended by International Seed Health Testing Association (1976). The fungi were identified as *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Rhizopus oryzae* and *Fusarium oxysporum*, based on their morphological and cultural characteristics. *Rhizopus stolonifer* was the most prominent while *Fusarium oxysporum* was the least. The result of the pathogenicity test carried out showed that the fungal organisms re-isolated had the same characteristics with those isolated originally from the diseased fruits; hence they are the causal agent of the fruit rot observed. This agrees with the report of (Amadi *et al.*, 2014) who reported that *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus stolonifera*, *Rhizopus oryzea* and *Fusarium oxysporum* were among the fungi associated with fruit rot of okra in Akwa South Iga, Anambra State. All the four pathogens were highly pathogenic. *Aspergillus niger* caused more severe rot in the inoculated okra fruit than any of the other pathogens. These organisms generally gain access in to the crops by several means, such as wounds and through natural openings on the surface of the produce (Amadi *et al.*, 2014).

Percentage disease incidence of the fruits collected showed, Wukari New Market had the highest percentage incidence in the study area with a total of 23%, followed by Wukari Old Market (19 %). The least percentage disease incidence was recorded in Allah-Yisa Market (0.7 %). The difference in the percentages may be due to the difference in the quantity of the produce and the storage methods which were locally weaved baskets and sacks. The four pathogens were found to be pathogenic, but *Aspergillus niger* was found to be more virulence with mycelia covering of 95.00%. The least was *Rhizopus oryzae* with mycelia covering of 76.33%. All the four pathogens were rated as highly pathogenic which also is in agreement with the work of (Agrawal, 2000).

Conclusion

It may be concluded from this study that *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Rhizopus oryzae* and *Fusarium oxysporum* are common pathogenic fungi which cause fruit rots of okra in the study area. The result from the pathogenicity test indicated that all the isolated fungi are highly pathogenic and are responsible for rot of okra fruit in Wukari. The pathogens are responsible for economic loss and can cause harm to unsuspecting consumers. Consumers are advised to look out for symptoms of okra fruit rots before consuming the fruits.

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